

Comparing Rule-Based and Data-Driven Ensemble Land Cover Maps across Europe

Mateo Moreno^{1,*}, Tomislav Hengl¹

¹ OpenGeoHub Foundation, Doorwerth, The Netherlands, mateo.moreno@opengeohub.org, tom.hengl@opengeohub.org

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Consistent and temporally coherent land cover data are essential for environmental monitoring, climate change impact assessment, and land management. Despite advances in remote sensing, global land cover products exhibit disagreements in legend design, spatial resolution, and classification methods, undermining their use for multi-temporal applications. This study evaluates two methodologically distinct approaches to ensemble land cover mapping at the global scale. The first approach implements a rule-based ensemble, in which thematic disagreements between input products are resolved by systematically defined expert decision rules that encode domain knowledge. The second approach applies a data-driven framework in which input land cover products serve as predictors, yielding harmonized, temporally consistent output through model optimization. The two products are assessed across European geographical regions with respect to thematic accuracy and class-level performance. This comparison highlights trade-offs between the interpretability inherent to rule-based and data-driven harmonization strategies, contributing to the development of more consistent and reliable land cover products for environmental applications.

Keywords: global land cover; remote sensing; ensemble modeling; data-driven.

1 Introduction

Land cover information is a fundamental input for a wide range of environmental applications, including climate modeling, biodiversity assessment, carbon accounting, and Earth system monitoring. Over the past two decades, numerous global land cover products have been derived from satellite imagery using different sensors, classification schemes, and methodological approaches, significantly advancing the availability of large-scale Earth observation data (Friedl et al. 2010, Bontemps et al. 2015).

Despite this progress, comparative studies have demonstrated that overall spatial agreement between major global products often remains below 60%, with disagreements concentrated in thematically complex regions such as wetlands and transitional vegetation (Fritz et al. 2011, Herold et al. 2008). These inconsistencies are largely attributable to differences in classification schemes, training data, and the interpretation of thematic boundaries, limiting the interoperability of land cover datasets and introducing uncertainty when they are combined or applied across temporal sequences. Ensemble-based approaches have been proposed to address these limitations by integrating multiple land cover products into a unified, more reliable representation,

reducing the uncertainty inherent in any single product (Pérez-Hoyos et al. 2020).

Such fusion approaches can be broadly divided into two categories. Rule-based methods resolve conflicts using expert-defined decision rules that draw on prior knowledge of class hierarchies and relative product reliability, offering transparency and reproducibility. Data-driven methods employ machine learning models trained on reference data to generate harmonized outputs, capturing complex nonlinear relationships across large spatial extents but at the cost of reduced interpretability (Maxwell et al. 2018). Despite the increasing adoption of both paradigms, systematic comparisons between rule-based and data-driven ensemble strategies remain scarce at continental scales. This study addresses this gap by comparing a rule-based and a data-driven approach to ensemble land cover mapping across continental Europe. Specifically, it aims to: (i) describe the design and implementation of both approaches; (ii) evaluate their thematic accuracy at level 1 across European biogeographical regions; and (iii) identify the complementary strengths and limitations of each strategy.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Rule-based ensemble

The rule-based product integrates approximately 20 global and regional land cover datasets through a structured hierarchy of expert-defined decision rules. Two primary backbone products provide the core classification: the GLAD GLCLUC dataset (30 m, 2000–2024, Potapov et al. 2022), and GLC_FCS30D (30 m, 1985–2022, Zhang et al. 2024). Thematic ancillary layers refine specific land cover types, including products for cropland, grassland, forest dynamics, and coastal wetlands (van Tricht et al. 2023, Parente et al. 2024, Bunting et al. 2018), supplemented by topographic auxiliary layers from GEDTM30 (Ho et al. 2025). Expert rules systematically resolve conflicts between overlapping inputs based on predefined thematic hierarchies and product reliability, producing a 40-class output, which is subsequently aggregated into eight level 1 classes for this comparison.

2.2 Data-driven ensemble

The data-driven product, or global ensemble land cover (GELC), trains a random forest classifier on approximately 72 million harmonized reference points spanning 2000–2022 (Simoes et al. 2025), derived from GLanCE (Stanimirova et al. 2023), Dynamic World (Brown et al. 2022), and WorldCereal (van Tricht et al. 2023). Labels are crosswalked to a unified 14-class legend compatible with IPCC reporting categories. Predictor covariates include

existing land-cover products and environmental variables, such as vegetation height and monthly land-surface temperature. Reference data quality is controlled through Bayesian map fusion and confident learning (Northcutt et al. 2021) to identify and exclude unreliable samples before training. The model produces annual predictions across 2000–2024, including discrete classifications and per-class probability surfaces.

2.3 Validation

The 14-class GELC output is aggregated to seven level 1 classes, and the 40-class rule-based product to eight level 1 classes. While the two legends are not identical, most classes are thematically equivalent, enabling a meaningful comparison. Both products are evaluated against a harmonized reference dataset compiled from multiple sources (Simoes et al. 2025), using overall accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. The rule-based product is evaluated on the 2020–2022 subset of the reference dataset, corresponding to the temporal coverage of its primary backbone products, while the data-driven product uses the full 2000–2022 reference pool, with a subset withheld for validation.

3 Results

Table 1 summarizes the class-level accuracy of both products at level 1. As noted in section 2.3, differences in temporal coverage and the use of non-independent validation data for the data-driven product limit the direct comparability of overall accuracy figures.

The rule-based product achieves an overall accuracy of 0.86 and a weighted F1 score of 0.86, while the data-driven product achieves an overall accuracy of 0.77 and a weighted F1 score of 0.77. At the class level, notable differences emerge. Forest is the best-performing class in both products, with F1 scores of 0.94 and 0.88, respectively, reflecting the thematic unambiguity and spatial extent of forest cover across European landscapes. Both products map water with high accuracy, achieving F1 scores of 0.86 and 0.94, respectively, consistent with the distinctiveness of open water surfaces. However, the lower producer's accuracy of the rule-based product (0.75) suggests that some water bodies are missed.

The rule-based product outperforms the data-driven product for cropland (0.82 vs 0.73) and grassland (0.68 vs 0.44), suggesting that expert rules are more effective at

Figure 1. Level 1 land cover classification for the reference year 2020 over three European tiles: Oslo, Norway (a, b), Toulouse, France (c, d), and Croatia (e, f). The left column (a, c, e) shows the rule-based ensemble product, and the right column (b, d, f) shows the data-driven ensemble (GELC) product.

Table 1. Class-level accuracy of the rule-based and data-driven ensemble products at level 1 over Europe. RB denotes a rule-based ensemble model, and DD denotes a data-driven ensemble model. UA denotes the user's accuracy, PA denotes the producer's accuracy, and OA denotes overall accuracy.

Class	UA _{RB}	PA _{RB}	F1 _{RB}	UA _{DD}	PA _{DD}	F1 _{DD}
Built-up	0.44	0.81	0.57	0.89	0.89	0.89
Cropland	0.81	0.83	0.82	0.79	0.68	0.73
Grassland	0.79	0.60	0.68	0.48	0.41	0.44
Forest	0.89	0.98	0.94	0.87	0.89	0.88
Sparsely vegetated	0.27	0.26	0.26	0.48	0.69	0.57
Wetland	0.25	0.61	0.35	0.81	0.62	0.71
Water	0.99	0.75	0.86	0.93	0.94	0.94
Coastal ecosystem	0.41	0.25	0.31	-	-	-
OA		0.86			0.77	
F1-weighted		0.86			0.77	

capturing the thematic nuances of vegetation management types. Conversely, the data-driven product achieves substantially higher F1 scores for built-up (0.89 vs 0.57) and wetland (0.71 vs 0.35), indicating that the data-driven approach better captures the spatial complexity of urban and wetland environments. Performance on sparsely vegetated and barren classes remains modest, with F1 scores of 0.26 and 0.57, respectively, consistent with the known difficulty of mapping transitional and heterogeneous land surface types. Overall accuracy figures should also be interpreted with caution, given the substantial class imbalance in the reference dataset, where dominant classes such as forest disproportionately influence aggregated metrics.

Figure 1 shows the level 1 land cover classification for both products over three selected tiles covering Oslo (Norway), Toulouse (France), and Croatia, for the reference year 2020. The rule-based and data-driven ensemble models produce broadly consistent spatial patterns across the three biogeographical regions: forest cover dominates the Oslo tile, mixed cropland and natural vegetation in the Toulouse tile, and a mosaic of forest, grassland, and cropland in the Croatian tile.

Visible differences between the two products are most apparent in transitional areas, particularly at the boundaries between grassland and sparse vegetation classes, reflecting the different strategies each approach employs to resolve thematic ambiguity. Differences are also apparent in built-up areas, where the rule-based product produces more spatially continuous and extensive urban extents compared to the data-driven product, which tends to map built-up areas in a more fragmented pattern.

4 Discussion

The results demonstrate that neither approach dominates across all land cover types, and that the choice of ensemble strategy has meaningful consequences for thematic accuracy and class-level performance. The rule-based ensemble performs consistently well for cropland and grassland, where the explicit encoding of domain knowledge through decision rules effectively leverages established thematic hierarchies and product-specific reliability estimates (Pérez-Hoyos et al. 2020).

The data-driven ensemble achieves substantially higher performance for built-up and wetland classes, suggesting that data-driven approaches better capture the spatial complexity of urban and wetland environments at the continental scale. The tendency of the rule-based product to produce more spatially continuous built-up extents, reflected in its higher producer's accuracy for this class (0.81), may be attributed to the deterministic application of urban delineation rules across input products, which systematically flags pixels meeting predefined urban criteria regardless of local land surface variability. Both products show modest performance for sparsely vegetated and barren classes, which may reflect the propagation of uncertainty from input products in regions of high inter-product disagreement (Fritz et al. 2011).

Several caveats apply. The data-driven product results are based on three representative tiles rather than a full continental production run, limiting the generalizability of findings. Furthermore, using non-independent validation data for the data-driven product may introduce optimism bias in class-level scores. A controlled comparison using a single harmonized validation dataset remains an important avenue for future work.

5 Conclusions

The comparison reveals complementary strengths. The rule-based product performs better on cropland and grassland, where domain knowledge effectively captures thematic nuances tied to land-management context. The data-driven product shows higher performance for built-up and wetland classes, where data-driven flexibility better accommodates spatial heterogeneity. Forest and water are mapped consistently well by both products, while sparsely vegetated and barren classes remain challenging for both approaches.

These findings highlight a fundamental trade-off: rule-based methods offer greater interpretability and semantic control, while data-driven methods provide greater adaptability across heterogeneous landscapes. Neither paradigm is universally superior, and the optimal choice depends on the thematic priorities of the intended application. Future work will extend the data-driven ensemble model to full global production, enabling a more comprehensive comparison using a single harmonized validation dataset. It will explore hybrid strategies combining the strengths of both approaches.

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